

4-Quinazolones IV. Synthesis of a Linear Furoquinazolone

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The synthesis of 2'-methyl-8-methoxy-2,3-diphenylfuro[4', 5' : 6, 7]-quinazolin-4(3H)-one (XVI) is described.

In Part III¹ of this series we reported the synthesis of some angular furoquinazolones. The present communication deals with the synthesis of a linear furoquinazolone, 2'-methyl-8-methoxy-2,3-diphenylfuro [4', 5' : 6, 7] quinazolin-4(3H)-one (XVI), based on our earlier procedure for developing a furan ring on an appropriate preformed quinazolone.

7-Allyloxy-8-methoxy-2,3-diphenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (XII) was considered the most suitable intermediate of our choice since the methoxyl group at 8-position can serve as a blocking group in the Claisen rearrangement to furnish 6-allyl-7-hydroxy-8-methoxy-2,3-diphenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (XIII) for building the desired furan ring. This synthetic sequence has been realised and for this purpose, the key intermediate (XII) was secured by two routes. 4-Benzyloxy-3-methoxy-2-aminobenzoic acid (II), obtained by the reduction of 4-benzyloxy-3-methoxy-2-nitrobenzoic acid² (I) with sodium dithionite, on Schotten-Baumann reaction with benzoyl chloride afforded 4-benzyloxy-3-methoxy-2-benzamido-benzoic acid (III). It was refluxed with acetic anhydride to give 7-benzyloxy-8-methoxy-2-phenyl-4H-3,1-benzoxazin-4-one (IV) which reacted with aniline and the resulting 7-benzyloxy-8-methoxy-2,3-diphenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (V) was debenzylated by catalytic hydrogenation to furnish 7-hydroxy-8-methoxy-2,3-diphenyl-quinazolin-4(3H)-one (VI). On treatment with allyl bromide in dimethylformamide in the presence of potassium carbonate, (VI) yielded 7-allyloxy-8-methoxy-2,3-diphenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (XII). Alternatively, 4-allyloxy-3-methoxy-2 nitrobenzaldehyde (VIII)

- I : R = CH₂Ph; R₁ = NO₂; R₂ = COOH
 II : R = CH₂Ph; R₁ = NH₂; R₂ = COOH
 III : R = CH₂Ph; R₁ = NHCOPh; R₂ = COOH
 VII : R = H; R₁ = NO₂; R₂ = CHO
 VIII : R = allyl; R₁ = NO₂; R₂ = CHO
 IX : R = allyl; R₁ = NO₂; R₂ = COOH
 X : R = allyl; R₁ = NH₂; R₂ = COOH
 XI : R = allyl; R₁ = NHCOPh; R₂ = COOH

1. S. K. P. Sinha and D. N. Chaudhury, *This Journal*, 1969, 46, 31.
2. D. H. Hay and L. C. Lobo, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 2246.

prepared by the interaction of allyl bromide in dimethylformamide with the sodium salt of 2-nitrovanillin³ (VII) or with (VII) itself in the presence of potassium carbonate, was oxidised

with silver oxide to 4-allyloxy-3-methoxy-2-nitrobenzoic acid (IX). Subsequent reduction with sodium dithionite gave 4-allyloxy-3-methoxy-2-aminobenzoic acid (X), the amino group of which was benzoylated. The product 4-allyloxy-3-methoxy-2-benzamidobenzoic acid (XI), on reacting with aniline in the presence of phosphorus trichloride afforded the intermediate allyloxyquinazolone (XII).

Transformation of (XII) to the furoquinazolinone (XVI) was effected by the method of Kaufman⁴. Claisen rearrangement of the allyloxy compound (XII) in boiling diethylaniline gave 6-allyl-7-hydroxy-8-methoxy-2,3-diphenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (XIII) which was acetylated with acetic anhydride in pyridine. The product, 7-acetoxy-6-allyl-8-methoxy-2,3-diphenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (XIV) in chloroform reacted with one molar equivalent of bromine to produce 7-acetoxy-6-(2',3'-dibromopropyl)-8-methoxy-2,3-diphenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (XV). Finally, on refluxing in alcoholic potassium hydroxide, (XV) was simultaneously dehalogenated and cyclised to yield 2'-methyl-8-methoxy-2',3'-diphenylfuro[4',5':6,7]-quinazolin-4(3H)-one (XVII).

EXPERIMENTAL

All m.ps. uncorrected. Light petroleum used had b.p. 60–80°.

4-Benzyloxy-3-methoxy-2-aminobenzoic acid (II).—To a solution of 4-benzyloxy-3-methoxy-2-nitrobenzoic acid² (I; 30 g.) in 10% aq. KOH (300 ml.), Na₂S₂O₄ was added in portions during the course of 0.5 hr when there was a rise of temperature which was not allowed to go beyond 80°; a white precipitate separated out after the addition was complete. The mixture was acidified (Congo red) with conc. HCl (100 ml.), cooled in ice-bath and the

3. P. K. Banerjee and D. N. Chaudhury, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1961, **26**, 4344.

4. K. D. Kaufman and L. R. Worden, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1961, **26**, 117 and later papers,

precipitated solid was filtered, washed with water and dried. Crystallisation from dilute ethanol or ethyl acetate gave pure II as colourless needles (23 g.; 80.6%), m.p. 171°. (Found : C, 66.1; H, 5.1; N, 5.2. Calc. for $C_{15}H_{15}O_4N$: C, 65.9; H, 5.4; N, 5.1%).

4-Benzylloxy-3-methoxy-2-benzamidobenzoic acid (III).—A solution of II (3 g.) in 10% aq. NaOH (30 ml.) was treated with $PhCOCl$ (5 ml.) and shaken vigorously until solid separated out. It was filtered, washed with a little cold water and triturated with 2N HCl. It was again filtered, washed with water and dried. Crystallisation from benzene-light petroleum yielded III as colourless needles (2.5 g.; 60.3%, m.p. 176°, with previous sintering at 174°. (Found : C, 70.3; H, 5.2. Calc. for $C_{22}H_{19}O_5N$: C, 70.0; H, 5.0%).

7-Benzylloxy-8-methoxy-2-phenyl-4H-3,1-benzoxazin-4-one (IV).—III (2 g.) was refluxed with Ac_2O (12 ml.) for 1 hr. and cooled in ice-bath when colourless needles separated out. These were filtered, washed with dry ether to yield IV (1.6 g.; 85%), m.p. 178°. The product was pure enough for the next step. An analytical sample, recrystallised from Ac_2O , melted at 181°. (Found : C, 73.4; H, 4.5. Calc. for $C_{22}H_{17}O_4N$: C, 73.5; H, 4.7%).

7-Benzylloxy-8-methoxy-2,3-diphenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (V).—IV (5 g.) was refluxed with $PhNH_2$ (10 ml.) in an oil-bath at 150° for 4 hr., cooled and the colourless crystalline material that separated was collected, washed with benzene and ether. Crystallisation from ethanol furnished V as colourless silky needles (4.5 g.; 75%), m.p. 193°, with previous sintering at 187°. (Found : C, 77.2; H, 5.2; N, 6.3. Calc. for $C_{23}H_{22}O_3N_2$: C, 77.4; H, 5.0; N, 6.4%).

7-Hydroxy-8-methoxy-2,3-diphenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (VI).—A solution of V (3 g.) in AcOH (4 ml.) was hydrogenated with 10% Pd-C (0.2 g.) at 70–80° under atm. press. until the theoretical amount of hydrogen was absorbed. The catalyst was filtered off, the filtrate concentrated under reduced pressure to a small bulk (15 ml.) and diluted with ice water. The solid that separated was collected, washed with water and crystallised from ethanol to afford VI as colourless irregular prisms (2 g.; 84%), m.p. 158°. (Found : C, 73.0; H, 4.8; N, 8.2. Calc. for $C_{21}H_{16}O_3N_2$: C, 73.2; H, 4.6; N, 8.1%).

4-Allyloxy-3-methoxy-2-nitrobenzaldehyde (VIII).—(a) A solution of 2-nitrovanillin³ (VII; 17 g.) in dry methanol (50 ml.) was added in portions to a solution of sodium methoxide, prepared from Na (2 g.) in dry methanol (50 ml.), and allowed to stand for 1 hr. Methanol was distilled off under reduced pressure, the white solid residue dissolved in DMF (100 ml.) and treated with allyl bromide (8.5 ml.) with occasional shaking. Next day, the solution was poured in ice-water (250 ml.) and the precipitated solid was filtered, washed with water and dried. Crystallisation from ethanol gave VIII as colourless needles (16.5 g.; 80.8%), m.p. 89°. (Found : C, 55.8; H, 4.8; N, 5.7. Calc. for $C_{11}H_{11}O_5N$: C, 55.6; H, 4.6; N, 5.9%).

(b) A mixture of VII (17 g.), allyl bromide (8.5 ml.) and K_2CO_3 (50 g.) in DMF (50 ml.) was left overnight and poured into water (250 ml.). The solid that precipitated was collected, washed with water and crystallised from ethanol to yield VIII as colourless needles (16 g.; 78%), m.p. and mixed m.p. 89°.

4-Allyloxy-3-methoxy-2-nitrobenzoic acid (IX).—To a refluxing solution of $AgNO_3$ (13.25 g.) in water (125 ml.), 15% aq. NaOH (25 ml.) was added when silver oxide formed.

To this was added VIII (8.15 g.) and anhydrous Na_2CO_3 (4 g.), and the mixture refluxed for 5 hr., filtered, the filtrate cooled and acidified. The precipitated solid was collected, washed with water and crystallised from ethanol to afford IX as plates (6 g.; 68%), m.p. 193° . (Found : C, 52.2; H, 4.5; N, 5.3. Calc. for $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{11}\text{O}_6\text{N}$: C, 52.1; H, 4.3; N, 5.5%).

4-*Allyloxy-3-methoxy-2-aminobenzoic acid* (X).— $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_4$ (20 g.) was added portionwise to a stirred solution of IX (6 g.) in 10% aq. KOH (60 ml.) at 70° during the course of 0.5 hr. After the addition, the solution was maintained at 80° for 1 hr., cooled and acidified (Congo red). The precipitated solid was filtered, washed with cold water and dried in an exiccator. Crystallisation from benzene gave X as colourless rectangular prisms (4 g.; 74%), m.p. 158° . (Found : C, 59.0; H, 5.6; N, 6.0. Calc. for $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{13}\text{O}_4\text{N}$: C, 59.2; H, 5.8; N, 6.2%).

4-*Allyloxy-3-methoxy-2-benzamidobenzoic acid* (XI).—A cooled solution of X (2 g.) in 10% aq. NaOH (40 ml.) was treated gradually with PhCoCl (7 ml.) and shaken vigorously until solid separated out. It was filtered, washed with water and thoroughly triturated with 2N HCl. It was again filtered, washed with cold water and crystallised from methanol to furnish XI as rectangular plates (1.6 g.; 54.8%), m.p. 112° . (Found : C, 66.2; H, 5.0; N, 4.0. Calc. for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{17}\text{O}_5\text{N}$: C, 66.0; H, 5.2; N, 4.3%).

7-*Allyloxy-8-methoxy-2,3-diphenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one* (XII).—(a) A solution of XI (4 g.) in dry CHCl_3 (30 ml.) was treated with PhNH_2 (1.75 ml.) and PCl_3 (0.5 ml.), and refluxed for 2 hr. on a steam bath, cooled and filtered from traces of suspended impurities. The filtrate was washed with dilute ammonia, water and dried (Na_2SO_4). Evaporation of the solvent left a solid residue which was crystallised from ethyl acetate-light petroleum to give XII as colourless needles (3.6 g.; 77%), m.p. 129° . (Found : C, 75.1; H, 5.0; N, 7.5. Calc. for $\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_3\text{N}_2$: C, 75.0; H, 5.2; N, 7.3%).

(b) To a solution of VI (5 g.) in DMF (50 ml.), allyl bromide (1.25 ml.) and K_2CO_3 (25 g.) were added and left overnight. It was then diluted with water and the precipitated solid was filtered, washed with water and dried in an exiccator. Crystallisation from ethyl acetate-light petroleum gave XII as colourless needles (4.6 g.; 80%), m.p. and mixed m.p. 129° .

6-*Allyl-7-hydroxy-8-methoxy-2,3-diphenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one* (XIII)—XII (5 g.) in PhNEt_2 (50 ml.) was refluxed for 4 hr. in CO_2 atmosphere in an oil bath at $215\text{--}220^\circ$ when a dark solution was obtained. It was filtered hot from traces of suspended impurities, the filtrate on being kept in the refrigerator overnight deposited crystalline solid (A) which was filtered and washed with ether.

The filtrate and the washings were combined, diluted with ether and extracted with 10% aq. NaOH (25 ml. $\times 3$). The alkaline extract, after washing with ether, was acidified with acetic acid and the precipitate (B) that separated out was collected, washed with water and dried in an exiccator. The solids (A) and (B) were combined and crystallised from acetic acid to yield XIII as colourless needles (3.5 g.; 70%), m.p. 224° . (Found : C, 75.3; H, 5.0; N, 7.1. Calc. for $\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_3\text{N}_2$: C, 75.0; H, 5.2; N, 7.3%).

7-Acetoxy-6-allyl-8-methoxy-2,3-diphenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (XIV).—A solution of XIII (3 g.) in dry pyridine (10 ml.) was treated with AC_2O (5 ml.), left overnight and then poured into crushed ice. The solid that separated out was filtered, washed with water and dried in an oven at 100° . Purification by chromatography of its benzene solution over alumina and subsequent crystallisation from methanol furnished pure XIV as colourless silky needles (2.8 g.; 85%), m.p. 170° . (Found : C, 73.1; H, 4.9; N, 6.7. Calc. for $\text{C}_{26}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_4\text{N}_2$: C, 73.2; H, 5.1; N, 6.5%).

7-Acetoxy-6-(2',3'-dibromopropyl)-8-methoxy-2,3-diphenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (XV).—To a stirred solution of XV (2 g.) in dry CHCl_3 (20 ml.) was added dropwise 2% v/v Br_2 in CHCl_3 (19 ml.; 1 ml. \equiv 5.6 ml. 0.888N $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$) until the colour of bromine was discharged. The solvent was evaporated at room temperature under reduced pressure and the gummy residue, on being rubbed with a few drops of ethanol, solidified. It was crystallised from ethanol to yield XV as off-white needles (1.6 g.; 58%), m.p. $173\text{--}174^\circ$. (Found : C, 53.5; H, 3.5; Br, 27.1. Calc. for $\text{C}_{26}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_4\text{N}_2\text{Br}_2$: C, 53.2; H, 3.7; Br, 27.3%).

2'-Methyl-8-methoxy-2,3-diphenylfuro[4',5':6,7]quinazolin-4(3H)-one (XVI).—XV (1.3 g.) was refluxed with a solution of KOH (1.5 g.) in ethanol (30 ml.) for 2 hr. on steam bath and filtered hot from traces of insoluble impurities. The filtrate was concentrated by distilling off the solvent (20 ml.) and on cooling, crystalline solid separated. Water (10 ml.) was gradually added when more solid deposited and the mixture was left in the refrigerator overnight. The solid was filtered, washed with water and dried in an exiccator. Purification by chromatography of its benzene solution over alumina followed by two crystallisations from benzene-light petroleum afforded the pure furo compound (XVI) as colourless prisms (0.55 g.; 60%), m.p. 188° . (Found : C, 75.6; H, 4.4; N, 7.1. Calc. for $\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_3\text{N}_2$: C, 75.4; H, 4.7; N, 7.3%).

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